

Singular Spectrum Analysis: A Signal Decomposition Method Applied for Parkinson's Disease

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Abstract—Parkinson's disease (PD) is a chronic neurodegenerative disorder that causes tremor, one of the main motor manifestations of the disease. To identify and evaluate tremor in an objective way is extremely important for an efficient monitoring of PD. For this, tremor must be separated/decomposed from motor signals collected to study characteristics related to this symptom in a direct and specific way. The objective of this work was to present, describe and exemplify the SSA method for the decomposition of motor signals collected from individuals with PD to obtain the signal that only represents the tremor of these individuals. SSA is a non-parametric method for time series decomposition. First, the method performs the decomposition of time series into elementary time series. Then, an appropriate grouping of the elementary time series is performed in an investigative way (eigenvalues analysis). Finally, reconstruction of elementary time series is performed to define the components of the decomposition. The SSA method was applied to a signal collected from an individual with PD during his interaction with a serious game to separate voluntary movement from involuntary movement of this individual. The results suggested that this method is extremely effective for this application, since the extracted tremor signal actually represents tremor caused by PD. In summary, applying this method enables the study of the tremor characteristics of individuals with PD in an objective and efficient way.

Keywords — *Singular Spectrum Analysis, Parkinson's disease, time series decomposition, tremor.*

INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a chronic neurodegenerative disorder characterized by the loss of dopaminergic neurons, responsible for the correct control of body movements. It is the second most common neurodegenerative disease in individuals over the age of 60 [1], and affects approximately 2% of this population [2]. The main motor symptoms of PD are tremor, bradykinesia, rigidity and postural instability, which negatively impact the lives of individuals affected by the disease.

Tremor is one of the most characteristic and most visible manifestations of PD. It is the first symptom perceived by the patients [3], and occurs in approximately 75% of these individuals. Tremor is a rhythmic and involuntary muscle contraction characterised by the oscillation of a body part at a frequency of 4 - 7 Hz [4].

The identification and objective quantification of motor symptoms of PD, such as tremor, is extremely important for an efficient assessment of individuals with PD. A very promising alternative for this is the use of devices that present inertial measurement units [5], [6], components responsible for collecting a part of the movement and storing it as numerical data [5]. In short, the motor symptoms of the disease can be detected by inertial sensors, capable of recording the movements of individuals in the form of time series.

In the case of tremor, besides the pure tremor movement (which is an involuntary movement), the recorded signals present other types of movements, interferences and artefacts. To extract tremor-related information from these signals it is necessary to use signal processing techniques, such as decomposition methods.

Time series decomposition involves deconstructing a time series into several components, each representing one of the underlying categories of a signal's patterns [7]. One of the most widely used signal decomposition methods is Singular Spectrum Analysis (SSA). SSA is a non-parametric method for the analysis of time series and digital images. This method decomposes a time series into a set of components that are grouped and interpreted, and the original time series is recovered by summing all its components [8].

SSA can be used to remove all periodic and trend components from a time series, leaving only a particular component, which may have real and interpretable meaning; and also to investigate the periodic components of a time series to understand the processes that generated the series [8], [9]. There are several application areas for SSA, such as economics, finance, mathematics, physics, meteorology, oceanology, and more recent ones such as engineering and medicine [9].

Thus, the aim of this paper was to present, describe and exemplify the SSA method for the decomposition of motor signals obtained from individuals with PD.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. General description of the SSA method

A general description of the method is presented below [8]–[11]. SSA performs the four steps illustrated in Fig. 1. The input X is an ordered collection of N real numbers (e.g., a time

series or a digital image), and the output is a decomposition of X into a sum of identifiable components: $X = X_1 + \dots + X_m$.

Fig. 1. Generic scheme of the SSA decomposition method.

Step 1 – Embedding: The starting point of SSA is the embedding of the time series X into a vector space of dimension L . As an example, $X = (x_1, \dots, x_N)$ and $T = \text{SSA}$ maps \mathbb{R}^N to the space of Hankel matrices $L \times K$ with equal values on the anti-diagonals. Thus, the embedding procedure constructs a sequence of vectors of the original time series using lagged copies of the scalar data. N is the length of the series, L is the length of the window (which is a parameter) and $K = N - L + 1$.

$$T(\text{SSA})(X) = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 & x_2 & x_3 & \dots & x_k \\ x_2 & x_3 & x_4 & \dots & x_{k+1} \\ x_3 & x_4 & x_5 & \dots & x_{k+2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_L & x_{L+1} & x_{L+2} & \dots & x_N \end{pmatrix}$$

Step 2 – Decomposition: The result of this step is the decomposition $\mathbf{X} = \sum_i \mathbf{X}_i$, $\mathbf{X}_i = \sigma_i \mathbf{U}_i \mathbf{V}_i^T$, where $\mathbf{U}_i \in \mathbb{R}^L$ and $\mathbf{V}_i \in \mathbb{R}^K$ are vectors such that $\|\mathbf{U}_i\| = 1$ and $\|\mathbf{V}_i\| = 1$ for all i and σ_i are non-negative numbers. This step performs the singular value decomposition (SVD) of the trajectory matrix and represents it as a sum of rank-one bi-orthogonal elementary matrices. Let $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}^T$, $\lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_L \geq 0$ be *eigenvalues* of the matrix \mathbf{S} , $d = \text{rank } \mathbf{X} = \max\{j : \lambda_j > 0\}$, $\mathbf{U}_1, \dots, \mathbf{U}_d$ be the corresponding *eigenvalues*, and $\mathbf{V}_j = \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{U}_j / \sqrt{\lambda_j}$, $j = 1, \dots, d$, be *factor vectors*. Denote $\mathbf{X}_j = \sqrt{\lambda_j} \mathbf{U}_j \mathbf{V}_j^T$. Then the SVD of the trajectory matrix \mathbf{X} can be written as $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{X}_1 + \dots + \mathbf{X}_d$. The triple $(\sqrt{\lambda_j}, \mathbf{U}_j, \mathbf{V}_j)$ consisting of the singular value $\sigma_j = \sqrt{\lambda_j}$, the left singular vector \mathbf{U}_j and the right singular vector \mathbf{V}_j of \mathbf{X} is called *jth eigentriple*.

Step 3 – Grouping: The grouping step corresponds to the division of the elementary matrices \mathbf{X}_j into several groups and summing the matrices within each group. The grouping procedure partitions the set of indices $\{1, \dots, d\}$ into m disjoint subsets $\{I_1, \dots, I_m\}$, with each group I_k containing a set of principal components $\{i_1, \dots, i_p\}$ representing specific components of the signal. Let $I_k = \{i_1, \dots, i_p\}$. Then the resulting matrix $\mathbf{X}I_k$ corresponding to the group I_k is defined as $\mathbf{X}I_k = \mathbf{X}i_1 + \dots + \mathbf{X}i_p$. These matrices are computed for

$I_k = I_1, \dots, I_m$ and the SVD expansion leads to the decomposition $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{X}I_1 + \dots + \mathbf{X}I_m$. Each $\mathbf{X}I_k$ represents a set of eigentriples which describes a specific component series in the original time series.

Step 4 – Reconstruction: The last step is to reconstruct the components of the original series. This is achieved by diagonal averaging of each $\mathbf{X}I_k$ to provide the k th component of the series X , where the n th sample is obtained by averaging over the cross-diagonal $i + j = \text{const} = n + 1$ of $\mathbf{X}I_k$. This is because each $\mathbf{X}I_k$ can be seen as the Hankel matrix for the corresponding embedded component series. Then the resulting decomposition of the initial object X is $X = X_1 + \dots + X_m$.

B. SSA used in R

The main function in The R Project for Statistical Computing [12] software for the SSA method is `ssa`, which constructs the `ssa` object that holds the decomposition and various auxiliary information. The typical function call of the `ssa` function in R is:

```
s <- ssa(x, L = (N + 1) %% 2, neig = NULL)
```

The main arguments are (N is the length of the series):

- `x` is an object to be decomposed (e.g. time series, digital image).
- `L` is a window length, which by default is fixed to half the length of the series.
- `neig` is the number of eigentriples desired. If `neig = NULL`, a default value, which depends on `L` and `N`, will be used.

The function returns a `ssa` object. The precise layout of the object is hidden, but identifying the indices of the elementary components is necessary for the next step (reconstruction). However, there are several fields that are available to users and can be extracted with the help of a `$` operator, namely:

- `s$sigma` is a vector of singular values.
- `(s$sigma)2` is a vector of eigenvalues.

In addition, it is possible to plot the eigenvalues using `plot(s)`, and the w-correlation matrix using `plot(wcor(s))`. This is done to find the parameters for the selection of principal components to group the elementary time series. Thus, the components that present similar eigenvalues are used for the grouping of the elementary time series.

The next step is reconstruction, performed with the `reconstruct` function. The basic function call is:

```
r <- reconstruct(s, groups = list(trend = 1:2, c(3:6, 9)))
```

The main arguments are:

- `s` is an `ssa` object that holds the decomposition.
- `groups` is a list of numeric vectors consisting of indices of the elementary components used for the reconstruction; the list entries can be named.

The function returns a list of reconstructed objects. The elements of the list have the same names as the elements of groups.

C. Exemplification of the method

To exemplify the application of the SSA method, a signal representing the flexion and extension movement of the hand, collected from an individual with PD during his interaction with a serious game was used. The movements of the individual were recorded by inertial sensors positioned on the back of the hand. The application of the serious game was approved by the Ethics Committee for Human Research of the Federal University of Uberlandia.

The signal was decomposed/separated into two other signals: one representing the voluntary movement (performed to play the serious game), and another representing the involuntary movement of the individual with PD (tremor).

RESULTS

Fig. 2 illustrates the time series representing the flexion and extension movement of the hand (original signal).

Fig. 2. Original signal of flexion and extension of the hand.

The code shown in the previous section that performs time series decomposition was applied to the signal shown in Fig. 2. First, the signal was decomposed using the `ssa` function and then it was reconstructed using the `reconstruct` function. The eigenvalues and the graphs were analysed to identify the elementary components that had similar eigenvalues.

The result of the reconstruction is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Decomposition of the hand flexion and extension movement signal (original) of an individual with PD during interaction with a serious game into two components: the voluntary movement, which represents the movement made by the player to control the game avatar; and the involuntary movement, represented by the tremor caused by the disease.

To verify that the extracted tremor signal actually represents a PD tremor, the power spectral density of the tremor was estimated (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Power spectral density of the tremor extracted from the original signal using the SSA decomposition method.

As a result, it is possible to note that the tremor density ranges between 4 and 7 Hz, which is the frequency range of a tremor originated from Parkinson's disease.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to present and exemplify the Singular Spectrum Analysis (SSA) method for the decomposition of a signal collected from an individual with PD. This is a method frequently used in several fields, such as economics, physics and geography; however, no study applying this method to signals collected from individuals with PD was found in the literature.

Time series decomposition allows extracting patterns and behaviours as components, enabling an understanding of the mechanisms that constitute the time series. Several techniques can be used for time series decomposition, such as Fourier analysis, Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) and Singular Spectrum Decomposition (SSD). However, Fourier analysis and EMD can provide data decomposition results with limited physical sense, i.e., components with unclear physical meaning. Furthermore, the components retrieved by these techniques can be affected by mode mixing, again interfering with the physical meaning of individual components [11]. Regarding the SSD technique, we first tested it before SSA to decompose the original signal presented in this paper, but we did not obtain successful results. In SSD, the selection of the fundamental parameters (window length and elementary component indices) is completely automated, and this resulted in components with no physical meaning.

In R software, the SSA package provides a set of fast and reliable implementations of various routines to perform time series decomposition and reconstruction. Usually the use of the package starts with decomposing time series using the `ssa` function. Then, an appropriate grouping of the elementary time series is performed, conducted in an investigative manner, for example, by analysing the decomposition plots (`plot(s)`) and the w-correlation matrix (`wcor(s)`). The last step includes the reconstruction of the time series using the selected grouping (`reconstruct`).

In this study, we applied the SSA method in a signal collected from an individual with PD to separate voluntary movement from involuntary movement. The results suggested

that this method is extremely effective for this application, since the extracted tremor signal actually represents a tremor caused by the disease. In addition, SSA avoided mode mixing and provided accurate separation between the components of the original signal evaluated. Due to the decomposition, it is possible to study the tremor characteristics of individuals with PD by analysing only the extracted signal that represents tremor.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the SSA method is very effective for decomposing signals collected from individuals with PD. The components extracted from the original signal faithfully represented the characteristic generated by PD, contributing to an objective evaluation of this symptom.

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